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Case study: Engineering education, Industry 4.0, security, and competencies-based assessment

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ABSTRACT

In recent years we have realized that the higher education teachers' motivation has grown. The research has reached classrooms. We are convinced that engineering undergraduate students could improve their learning by applying new rules and new ways of assessment. This study presents a specific case where the training is updated with techniques and ideas coming from the industry world. On the one hand, we compare the activities in engineering classes with the aspects of industry 4.0, such as the sensors as students receiving knowledge and acquiring competencies, and the tutors as actuators improving the training. On the other hand, we have proposed students from the 3rd year, to be competencies' evaluators. This could be achieved when they develop a team work made by themselves, including some aspects of realistic learning, like activity, reality, principle of levels, interconnection, interactivity, and guiding principle.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Mathematics in Engineering Education, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Engineering education, Industry 4.0, competencies-based assessment

INTRODUCTION

One of the characteristics of today's education is that it focuses on the student. As is well known, we have moved from a teacher-centred teaching (see *Fig. 1*) to one in which the centre is the student, who is responsible for his own learning, like a distributed system (see *Fig. 2*). In this way, a collective teaching in the past, when many were trained, has been individualized and tailored to each one; or rather, each student makes his learning to his measure, without harming the rest. Education has been decentralized to a system of self-organization. In addition to this, the educational system we use tries not to be an additive educational system, since it

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does not seek to add and overlap contents in successive sessions, but the student acquires the competences that he needs to be a competent professional.

Fig. 1. Centralized system

Fig. 2. Distributed system

In recent years, the digitization of factories has led to the concept of Industry 4.0. This term includes technologies such as smart industry and smart products, cyber-physical systems (CPS), Internet of Things (IoT), Internet of everything (IoE), cybersecurity, the cloud, hyperconnectivity, big data, 3D printing or robotics.

Industry 4.0 is the communication within an industrial plant, the processing of production data to improve productivity, effectiveness and quality of the final product or service. It implies the improvement of the relationships within the supply chains. In short, the interrelation between suppliers, manufacturers and final consumers, makes an Industry 4.0.

Our classrooms are no longer a physical space as we also work in cyber-classrooms. Even in cases where an online platform is only used in the most basic way (text files and tasks to be delivered), each trainer is aware of the student's activities and even the time and place from which he or she is connected. The classroom has become a "cyber-physical system" in which we have sensors to record students' activity and actuators that return feedback, in the form of explanations or marks. That is, we use the sensors to monitor the students and the actuators to change the "parameters" that do not return the proper output.

The progressive implementation of the IoE makes some concepts, such as the computer virus and malware understandable and everyday items. We are all connected. We have proposed our engineering students a Realistic Mathematics Education (RME), related to their engineering knowledge and based on cybersecurity [1], CPS [2], and in general, industry 4.0.

The connection to mobile devices, the IoE, and the invisible information and communication systems embedded in our environment have definitely changed the educational paradigm. All these changes have come very directly to engineering education. In recent years research and innovation has been carried out in engineering, in order to improve the existing system.

This study presents theoretical and empirical aspects that bring changes in which the same ideas of Industry 4.0 have led to an educational system 4.0. In several courses of engineering degrees, in different subjects, a hybrid teaching was carried out, with one traditional part and another with these characteristics. We have analyzed the

results at the end of the semester. Some of the grades obtained, when evaluating the competences of the students with rubrics or several tests that include multiple choice questions led us to think that students are not prepared for this type of education, and also that our educational system is not fully adapted to the new evaluation system.

In this experience with undergraduate students, the acquisition of the 8 math competencies was assessed [3]. The results showed that the students who usually obtained better grades were the ones that made worse results in the tests. We will also detail and analyze some of the causes that could lead to these results.

1 ASSESSMENT IN MATHEMATICS

The assessment process has a long history in education and it has attracted increased attention from teachers in mathematics. It has been widely studied. Different tools have defined different approaches to assessment, some examples are the tests, on-demand tasks, the portfolio, performance assessment or what was called authentic assessment, between others [4].

Mogen Niss, in [5], refers to the assessment mode as a vector with the following set of components:

1. Subject of assessment (who is assessed): Individual student or a group of students.
2. Objects of assessment (what is assessed): Mathematical facts, methods and techniques for obtaining mathematical results, or standard mathematical applications, modelling, and problem solving.
3. Items of assessment (what kinds of output are assessed): tasks, and especially questionnaires, exercises, problems, oral presentations, or small programs with specific software, constitute the predominant items of assessment.
4. Occasions of assessment (when does assessment take place): we may distinguish between continuous assessment and discrete assessment using the category of time.
5. Procedures and circumstances of assessment (what happens where and who is expected to do what?): As far as continuous assessment is concerned, students produce the items of assessment, whether material (e.g. written texts) or immaterial (e.g. activity level in class) either directly in the classroom or as homework. Assessment conditions should be just and allow for reliable judgement as well as for objective and easy marking, grading, and comparison of students' performance
6. Judging and recording in assessment (what is emphasized): what is emphasized is students' mastery of the content and ability explicitly or implicitly established in connection with the curriculum. The emphasis on completeness and correctness (reasoning, explanation, exposition, communication, methods, techniques, and procedures involved in arriving at the goals).
7. Reporting of assessment outcomes (what is reported to whom?): What is typically reported is the assessment record in its most aggregate and terse forms (marks and grades, accompanied, perhaps, by general statements). Such additional information can include nuances, explanations, comments, or suggestions which provide a broader and more comprehensive background for decisions and actions.

In the case of the group of teachers that have developed this study, we teach in industrial engineering degrees, specifically in electrical, electronic and automatic, mechanical, and chemical engineering degrees. We have detailed the components of our proposal for the vector defined by Niss in Table 1.

Table 1. Assessment features during our course

Assessment mode	Our case
Subject	Group of students and individual students.
Objects	Applications to real life and problem solving.
Items	Oral presentations and a questionnaire.
Occasions	Discrete assessment.
Procedures and circumstances	Immaterial (with an oral interview) by the teachers and by the fellow students, and material (some tests).
Judging and recording	Degree of correctness (reasoning, explanation, exposition, communication, methods, techniques, and procedures) of students.
Reporting	Nuances, explanations, comments, and suggestions by the teacher and by the fellow students.

To make this assessment possible, we have proposed the students the development of a team work in which the following aspects should be included ([6], [7]):

1. Activity: each student is an active participant in his own learning process.
2. Reality: apply the themes and topics of the subjects to the resolution of real problems.
3. Principle of levels: students go through several levels of understanding (in the process of learning) until they are able to see the whole problem. This principle is closely related to mathematical models, which establish a bridge between more purely formal and applied teaching.
4. Interconnection: the topics of the different subjects of the degree are integrated with each other. They are not watertight compartments within the curriculum of the subject.
5. Interactivity: Learning is a social activity and not just an individual task.
6. Guiding principle: it is related to the proactive role of teacher-tutor, as he is the responsible of guiding the teaching-learning trajectory.

Moreover, we asked students to specify the mathematical topic of the work, and they must also develop the 8 competencies in their work, i.e., these competencies will be the common thread of the work.

As final task of the team work, students have to propose a questionnaire in which the 8 competencies are assessed, with at least one multiple-choice question per competence. These questionnaires will be filled by the rest of students' fellows.

During the development of the team work, there are some sessions student vs. tutor to improve the work, the teacher-tutor revises the on-going work and make students to modify some parts, according with the basis of the requested work.

2 COMPETENCIES-BASED ASSESSMENT

During the course, when we study optimization concepts, we have proposed the students a questionnaire, similar to the one that they will implement later on. The questionnaire with multiple choice questions evaluates the competencies.

In detail, the specific proposed problem was to find the point of the band \overline{AB} where it will be easier to score a goal in the p goal (considering a football field with the shape and dimensions of the *Fig. 3*) [8].

Fig. 3. Football field with the dimensions for the proposed problem

Some of the questions were the following:

1. How would you solve the problem of knowing the point of the band from which to score the goal?
 - (a) It is a problem of football strategy.
 - (b) It is a problem of probabilities, from the studies of the last parties.
 - (c) It is a problem that is solved if you understand football and you like it.
 - (d) We can solve it mathematically.
2. What would be the reasoning of the problem?
 - (a) We draw a straight line from each point of the band \overline{AB} to the goal to obtain the optimum (although if the shot is angled we should also consider the curves).
 - (b) As $c \cong 2b$, the point from which it is easier to score goal is the centre of the band.
 - (c) The easiest point will be the one with the highest angle, since if we are in A it is impossible to get the ball through the goal. As we go towards B it becomes easier.
 - (d) None of the above. We are missing data on the problem.
3. Problem statement:
 - (a) The higher the angle the goal is seen from the band, the easier it will be to score. We must, therefore, maximize the angle $\varphi = \varphi_1 - \varphi_2$.
 - (b) It is necessary to take into account the angle β from which it is thrown to goal and that angle is the one that must be maximum.
 - (a) We should use the Thales's theorem (similar triangles) to solve the problem.
 - (b) The statement is incomplete and can not be resolved if we do not have more information.

Fig. 2. Graphic from question 3. (a)

Fig. 3. Graphic from question 3. (b)

4. Solving the problem:

- (a) Since the tangent is a growing function in $[0, \frac{\pi}{2})$, the problem is equivalent to calculating the maximum of φ and of $\text{tg } \varphi$.
- (b) It is a question of solving an optimization problem, in which the minimum distance from the line \overline{AB} to the goal p must be calculated.
- (c) Since we have right-angled triangles, we must solve a problem of least squares (that we obtain when using the theorem of Pythagoras).
- (d) We must know the dimensions of the football field to obtain the requested value.

5. Determine which of the following models or methods allows us to solve the problem correctly:

- (a) We must solve a problem of optimization of a variable, which is the distance to the goal.
- (b) We must solve an optimization problem in which the angle with which the goal is seen from the band should be maximum.
- (c) We must solve an optimization problem in which the angle forming the line \overline{AB} with the ball trajectory must be maximum.
- (d) It can be solved using the relationships between the dimensions of the field, since they are standard and equal in all football fields.

6. Select which of the following expressions gives us the objective function of the problem:

- (a) $\text{tg } \varphi = \frac{\text{tg } \varphi_1 - \text{tg } \varphi_2}{1 + \text{tg } \varphi_1 \text{tg } \varphi_2} = \frac{ax}{x^2 + (a+b)b} = f(x)$
- (b) $\text{tg } \beta = \frac{\text{sen } \beta}{\text{cos } \beta} = \frac{b/x}{x/a} = f(x)$
- (c) $d(\overline{AB}, p) = \sqrt{(x-a)^2 - (x-b)^2} = f(x)$
- (d) $d(\overline{AB}, p) = \sqrt{(x-a)^2 - (y-b)^2} = f(x, y)$

After seeing and solving that questionnaire, students must define a similar one related to their team work. Some of them do not understand the concept of competence, others made questions relate to topics of the work, and others to the curricula of the course. As time passes, students learn from each other, they ask the tutor about how to make the test, and they finally get the questionnaire. The average mark obtained by the students that completed this specific test was 5.71/10. The amount of students that participated was 21 out of 46. These students were more prepared to develop their own questions.

3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In recent years the assessment process has get more importance, as it establish the difference between different educational systems. We have proposed our students from industrial engineering degrees to assess and be assessed in competencies. The proposed method could be substantially improved, but we tried to start to have the chance to make a better assessment system.

Students from the 3rd year of chemical engineering have participated in this experience. They developed a team work and they proposed a multiple-choice questionnaire to assess the 8 mathematical competencies.

45 students have participated on this course. They were organized in 16 groups. Each group has proposed a multiple-choice questionnaire to be completed by their fellows. The average grade from these competence-based activities was 6.69, but the average in the rest of assessment activities (different problems solved by hand or with a CAS) was 8.22.

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